

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№8

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

2025

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 665 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2025-yil 1-avgustda ruxsat etildi.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldix'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

- Salimov Okil Umrzokovich**, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilkhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Khusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Rakhimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridakhon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

Smart-logistika texnologiyalarini joriy etish orqali oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarini yetkazib berish tizimini optimallashtirish (Toshkent viloyati misolida).....	14
Mavlanov Sobirjon Pardabayevich	
Tijorat banklarida korporativ boshqaruvning xalqaro tamoyillari asosida boshqaruv sifatini oshirish	20
Sattarov Umirzoq	
Современные банковские продукты	24
Хужамуратов Аббос Мардонович	
Amerika qo'shma shtatlarining ijtimoiy himoya tizimi.....	29
Abdullayeva Sayora Aleksandrovna	
Совершенствование рынка услуг высшего образования как фактор повышения занятости населения в условиях цифровой экономики.....	33
Ибрагимов Тимур Ибодуллаевич, Асланова Дилбар Хасановна	
Iqtisodiy fanlarni o'qitishda interaktiv metodlarning qo'llanilishi va ularning samaradorligi.....	39
Kabulov Baxram Kuzibaevich	
Korxonalarda raqobat razvedkasi tizimlarini rivojlantirishda innovatsion raqamli texnologiyalarining o'rni.....	45
Tursunxo'jayev Sardor Jamoliddin o'g'li	
O'zbekiston banklarida sun'iy intellekt foydalanish samaradorligini oshirish.....	51
Kamolov Sardorbek Davlatjon o'g'li	
Agrar korxonalar xo'jalik faoliyatida risklarni boshqarish bo'yicha samarali boshqaruv qarorlarini qabul qilishning metodologik asoslari.....	59
Baymirzaev Dilmurod Nematovich	
Основные направления инвестиционной политики Узбекистана в соответствии со стратегией-2030	66
Исомов Б. С.	
Tashish va saqlash xizmatlarini ko'rsatuvchi korxonalarda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish holati.....	70
Rajabov Orzujon Mamasoliyevich	
Ijtimoiy infratuzilmani modernizatsiya qilishda DXSHning o'rni: madaniyat va sport sohasida imkoniyatlar	78
Baykalonov Jalil G'aybulloevich	
Анализ состояния и перспективы развития активного и спортивного туризма в Узбекистане.....	93
Бойко Фарида Чингисовна, Ивонина Наталья Викторовна	
Переоценка и фальсификация стоимости имущества: международные практики, риски и пути решения.....	99
Мансурова Сайёра Бахтияровна	
Hudud sanoati tarkibiy o'zgarishlarini prognozlash usuli.....	106
Djumayev Farrux Toshmuratovich	
Углеродный след и декарбонизация промышленности Узбекистана: роль возобновляемой энергетики и международный опыт	111
Авезова Нилуфар Раббанакулловна, Ощепкова Эльвира Ахтемовна, С.М. Махмудов, А.А. Холиков, Авезова Нилуфар Раббанакулловна	
The process of developing startups based on management principles	119
Илхамов Azizbek Yodgor o'g'li	
The impact of economic policy on non-performing loans: the case of Uzbekistan.....	126
Jalalov Mashkhurbek Gaybullo ugli	
Основные направления инвестиционной политики Узбекистана в соответствии со стратегией-2030	134
Исомов Б. С.	

Ko'p kvartirali uylarni boshqaruv organlari tomonidan aholiga sifatli xizmat ko'rsatishni qo'llab quvvatlashni takomillashtirish	138
Umarov Begzodbek Jaloldinovich	
O'zbekistonda iqtisodiyotni innovatsion rivojlantirishning institutsional asoslari.....	143
Fayzullayev Jonibek Negmatullayevich	
Davlat - xususiy sheriklik loyihalarning samaradorligini oshirish.....	150
Tursunov Imomnazar Egamberdiyevich, Hamroyev G'ayratjon Sultonovich	
O'zbekiston sug'urta bozorida hayot sug'urtasi xizmatlarining rivojlanish tendensiyalari va istiqbollari.....	155
Bazarov Zakir Xonqulovich	
Tijorat banklari likvidligini tartibga solish yo'llari.....	160
Tursunpo'latov Sohibnazar Kasimjon o'g'li, Nomozova Mohinur Maxmud qizi	
Atrof-muhit ifloslanishini kamaytirishda yashil moliya vositalarining roli: xalqaro tajriba va O'zbekiston imkoniyatlari	163
Yuldasheva Madina Tohir Qizi	
Geofazoviy ma'lumotlar asosida hududlarning farovonlik darajasini aniqlash	173
Toymasov Zufarjon Zokir o'g'li	
Методы и критерии оценки эффективности конкурентоспособности предприятия	179
Кучаров Абдор Сабиржанович, Бобожонов Азиз Бабаханович, Алижанова Камила Тохир кизи	
Korxonalarda innovatsion jarayonlarni boshqarishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmini takomillashtirish.....	187
Narbayeva Dilnoza Darvishaliyevna	
Development of entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan: management strategies in the context of economic reforms.....	192
Ibragimova Saida Ilkhomovna	
Aloqa korxonalarini xizmat faoliyatida diversifikatsiya qilishning ilmiy baholash usullari va ulardan foydalanish.....	197
Tursunova Mastura Taxirovna	
Developing effective marketing strategies for tourism development in Uzbekistan	204
Fayzullayev Nodirbek Baxtiyor o'g'li	
Yakka tartibdagi tadbirkorlarni soliqqa tortish mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish masalalari.....	208
Yuldashev Yashnarjon Xolmirzayevich	
Yoshlar sanoat va tadbirkorlik zonalarida investitsiya loyihalarini bank kreditlari orqali moliyalashtirish.....	212
Jamalova Dilnoza Egamberdiyevna	
Цифровизации системы стратегического управления предприятий нефтегазовой отрасли Республики Узбекистан.....	217
Азимов Кабул	
Индекс устойчивости региона против бедности (poverty resilience index – pri): на примере бухарской области Республики Узбекистан (2024)	223
Мухамедова Мадинабону Мехридиновна	
Экономические аспекты внедрения цифровых технологий в полиграфии.....	230
Юсупхужаева Шахноза Музаффар кизи	
Mintaqalararo iqtisodiy hamkorlikni shakllantirish va barqaror rivojlantirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari.....	233
Sattorov R. A.	
Web3'da real vaqt ma'lumot sinxronizatsiyasi — tarmoqdagi kechikishlar va ularni kamaytirish texnologiyalari.....	240
Raimov Ulugbek Yorqinbek o'g'li	
Tijorat banklarining likvidligini tartibga solish amaliyotining dolzarb masalalari	246
Sayfutdinov Bobur Nodirovich	
Tijorat banklarining investitsion jozibadorligini oshirish yo'llari.....	255
Yuldoshev Otabek Jovli o'g'li	

Tijorat banklarining investitsion faolligini oshirish yo'llari.....	261
Ortiqov Sidiqjon Xolmurodovich	
Innovatsion yondashuvlar orqali davlat xaridlarida iqtisodiy samaradorlikni oshirish	266
Kurbonbekov Sardorbek Ravshanovich	
Hududlarda barqaror rivojlanish nazariyalarining sanoat korxonalarini faoliyatiga ta'siri	270
Sadriddinov Baxtiyor Shamshiddin o'g'li	
Turizm platformalarining raqobatbardoshligini oshirishda zamonaviy kontent va raqamli marketing strategiyalarining integratsiyalashgan yondashuvi.....	277
Dadamirzayev Sarvarbek Ulug'bek o'g'li	
Bank xizmatlarida innovatsion texnologiyalarni kengaytirish yo'nalishlari.....	283
Almosova Shohista Jobirovna	
Модели организации казначейства в ведущих стран мира.....	288
Сагдиев Равшан Сайфуллаевич	
Paxta-to'qimachilik klasterlari faoliyatini nazariy jihatlarini va rivojlantirish yo'llari.....	302
B.Sh.Shadmanov	
Qurilish sanoatini rivojlantirishda tabiiy resurslardan kompleks foydalanishning ahamiyati.....	307
Yuldasheva Mexrunisa Kasimjan qizi	
Yangi O'zbekistonning "Yashil" iqtisodiyoti: qiyosiy tahlilning asosiy tendentsiyalari	313
Ro'ziyeva Dilfuza Toshemirovna	
Oliy ta'limda raqamli texnologiyalarning muammolari va uni bartaraf etish yo'nalishlari.....	318
Abduraxmanova Malika Abdujaparovna	
Namangan viloyatining Farg'ona vodiysi qo'shni hududlari bilan iqtisodiy hamkorligining hozirgi holati va rivojlantiruvchi omillari	323
Sattarov R.A.	
Desentralizatsiyalangan ma'lumot almashish protokollari: IPFS, Filecoin va Arweave tahlili	328
Raimov Ulug'bek Yorqinbek o'g'li	
Transport xizmatlari ko'rsatish biznes-jarayonlarini raqamli transformasiya talablari asosida takomillashtirish.....	333
Komilov Asror Akmalovich	
Empowering the Future: Assessing the Role of Automation, Internet of Things (IoT), and Demand Management in Enhancing Energy Efficiency of Smart Grids.....	338
Khakimjanova Surayyo Khabibullayevna	
Ta'lim jarayonida sun'iy intellektdan foydalanish tajribalari (xalqaro va mahalliy misollar)	345
Madaminov Shoxruxbek Ma'rufjon o'g'li	
Zamonaviy sharoitlarda uy-joy fondini boshqarishning moliyaviy mexanizmini takomillashtirish	352
Inoyatova Durdona Shoxaydarovna, Karimova Aziza A'zamiddin qizi	
Mijozlar tajribasini yaxshilashda raqamli integratsiya strategiyalari: "O'zbektelekom" AK tajribasi.....	358
Islamov Javlon Rasulovich	
Tijorat banklari orqali jinoiy yo'l bilan olingan daromadlarni legallashtirishga qarshi kurashish mexanizmlari.....	361
Rustamov Sunnatillo Rustamovich	
Yashil iqtisodiyot barqaror rivojlanish omili sifatida: Yevropa tajribasi.....	368
Turobjanov Murodjon Maxammadjanovich	
Ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy barqarorlikka erishishda kichik biznes va mahalla hamkorligi modellarini takomillashtirish	373
Murotov Nodir Xujamqulovich	
Xalqaro moliya institutlarining O'zbekiston bank sektori va iqtisodiyotiga ta'siri: YETTB faoliyati misolida tahlil.....	378
Alimov Azizbek Alievich	
Bankrotlik xavfini tahlil qilish modellari.....	386
Nasiriddinov Bahouddin Nuriddinovich	

Xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalarida sifat va samaradorlikni oshirishni takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	393
Burxonova Nargiza Mirshohid qizi	
Iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash jarayonida bank tizimi islohotlari va ularni boshqarish strategiyalari.....	400
Hamroyev Xurshid Jalilovich	
“Temir yo'l transportida MHXSni joriy etishning ahamiyati va milliy standartlar bilan taqqoslama tahlili”	405
Babaxalov Norbo'ta Eshnazarovich	
Banking and financial services in the process of economic development digitalization and its advantages and security of the process	409
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, Baxanurov Oqil Odil og'li	
Kichik biznesda moliyaviy barqarorlikni ta'minlashdagi asosiy muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo'llari.....	416
Abduvosit Omonboyev	
“Futurologiya va mintaqaviy iqtisodiy transformatsiya: Markaziy Osiyoda O'zbekistonning strategik senariylari”	421
Siddiqov Abdusalom Abdumalikovich	
Kichik biznes subyektlarini bank kreditlari orqali qo'llab-quvvatlashning rivojlangan xorijiy davlatlar tajribalari.....	425
Irgasheva Nigora Akbarovna	
Туристская мобильность стран персидского залива как устойчивый и перспективный источник въездного туризма в Узбекистан	434
Додиев Феруз, Голышева Елена Вячеславовна	
Turistik erkin iqtisodiy zonalarda investitsiya loyihalarini amalga oshirish: Imkoniyatlar, muammolar va istiqbollar	443
Xoliqov Dostonbek Rustam o'g'li	
Oliy ta'limda davlat-xususiy sheriklik: moliyalashtirish modelini modernizatsiya qilish yo'nalishlari.....	449
Bozorov Alisher O'zimurotovich	
Xalqaro raqamli intergatsiya, raqamlashtirish sharoitida tijorat banklari faoliyati tahlili	455
Turapov Bahromjon Alisher o'g'li	
To'g'ridan-to'g'ri xorijiy investitsiyalar – iqtisodiyot taraqqiyotining muhim omili.....	461
Mamatkulova Nodira Maxkamovna	
Davlat xaridlari ishtirokchilarining elektron-skoring tizimi.....	465
Mamasoliyev Abrorbek Abdug'ani o'g'li	
Qishloq xo'jalik korxonalarida melioratsiya xarajatlari xisobining muammolari va yechimlari.....	469
Baxriev Muxiddin Sheralievich	
O'zbek banklarining xarajatlar samaradorligini stoxastik chegara modelida baholash.....	481
Xannayev Sherzod	
Практические подходы к выявлению и оценке налоговых рисков на основе сегментации деятельности налогоплательщиков.....	490
Голубова Ольга Сергеевна, Элбаева Мукаддас Рашидовна	
Iqtisodiyot tarmoqlarida investitsiyalardan samarali foydalanishni tashkil etish chora-tadbirlari va investitsiyalarni jalb qilish istiqbollari.....	496
No'monjonova Muazzam Maxbubjon qizi	
Empowering the future: The impact of automation, iot, and demand management on energy efficiency in smart grids.....	501
Khakimjanova Surayyo Khabibullayevna	
Institutsional o'zgarishlar sharoitida aholi daromadlari tarkibining oshishi va daromadlar tengsizligini kamaytirishning istiqbolli yo'nalishlari.....	508
Ergasheva Nafisa Baxridinovna	
Международные индексы, определяющие цифровое развитие страны	513
Тальятова Диёра Боходир кизи	

Sog'liqni saqlash sohasida davlat-xususiy sheriklik instituti orqali investitsiya loiyhalarini moliyalashtirishda moliyaviy-iqtisodiy samaradorligini baholash metodologiyasi	517
Karabayev Sanjar Abdusamatovich	
Управление качеством в технологических стартапах: Баланс между скоростью и надежностью	527
Хамидуллина Гульнора Рафкатовна, Раджабов Темур Рустамович, Носиров Илхом Аббосович	
Namangan viloyatida iqtisodiy integratsiyani jarayonida eksport va import operatsiyalarining tahlili	535
Adashev Azimjon O'rinboevich	
Korxonalarda kadrlar tayyorlash ijrosidagi mavjud muammolar va kadrlar siyosatining takomillashtirib borish xususiyatlari	541
Mamatqulov Rustam Muxammadkarimovich	
Yashirin iqtisodiyot tushunchasi, turlari va shakllanish omillari hamda uning iqtisodiyotga ta'siri.....	546
Malikov Abdulaziz Toxirjon o'g'li, S.A. Zakirova	
The purpose of assessing a person's entrepreneurial capacity is to classify their quality characteristics	562
Mansur Matkarimov, Qaxramon Madraximov, Sherjon Sherjonov, Jahongirbek Nurjonov	
Challenges in enhancing the efficient use of economic resources in agriculture within an innovative economy framework.....	568
Nodira Abdullayevna Eshquvattova	
Оценка эффективности существующих методов стратегического управления проектами	573
Мансурова Севара Мансуровна	
Создаются благоприятные условия для индивидуальных предпринимателей и самозанятых лиц	577
Батыров Фархад Бакытович	
Sug'urta kompaniyalarining moliyaviy barqarorligini oshirish metodologiyasini takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	593
Haqberdiyev Bekzod O'ktamovich	
Toshkent viloyatida metal bozorining rivojlanishi va unda kichik biznesning o'rni	600
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
Mechanisms for ensuring employment in the services sector through the development of small business and private entrepreneurship.....	606
Turabekov Sokhibjon Sherboy ugli, Abdukhalikov Ulugbek Abdukhalikovich	
Tijorat banklarini raqamlatirish sharoitida inson resurslarini boshqarishning innovatsion yondashuvlari (BRB misolida)	611
Azimov Asrorjon Muzaffarjonovich	
The importance and current state of accounting and auditing of liabilities in enterprises	616
Khaliqnazarova Gulnaz Jalgasbay qizi	
Kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikda xotin-qizlarning barqaror bandlik darajasining ekonometrik tahlili.....	622
Xoliyorova Shoxista Qahramon qizi	
Moliyaviy bozor ishtirokchilari faoliyatini samarali boshqarishda innovatsion moliyaviy vosita va metodlarning qo'llanilishi.....	627
Hotamqulova Madina Sanjar qizi	
Oliy ta'limga investitsiya kiritishning asosiy shakl va mexanizmlari	631
Almardanov Ulug'bek Qudrat o'g'li	
"Yashil" iqtisodiyotning metodologik asoslari.....	635
Babakulov Bahromqul Mamatkulovich, Sharipov Sardor Begmaxmat o'g'li, Boymurodov Jonon Komiljonovich	
O'zbekiston sharoitida davlat xaridlarini yanada rivojlantirish istiqbollari	641
Turganbaev Nursulton Bayram uli	

Tijorat banklarida jismoniy shaxslarga ko'rsatiladigan xizmatlar raqamli transformatsiyaning joriy holati tahlili	645
Qurbonov Alisher Samadovich	
Инновационные формы сотрудничества образования и индустрии для формирования компетенций в сфере устойчивого туризма: Опыт и перспективы Узбекистана.....	653
Бухарова Нигора Газиевна	
Muzey sohasida tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlar nazariyasi va ularni madaniy meros va muzeyshunoslik sohasiga tatbiq etish	657
Asadova Nigora Mehridin qizi	
Internet banking adoption in Uzbekistan	661
Karimov Erkin Yusubovich	

INTERNET BANKING ADOPTION IN UZBEKISTAN

Karimov Erkin Yusubovich

Head of "CHINA GRANT" Limited Liability Company

ORCID: 0009-0001-8338-7946

E-mail: enrike_2004@mail.ru

Abstract: This research paper presents an empirical study of the various factors influencing the adoption of internet banking facilities among customers in Uzbekistan. The variables examined for the research were perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, trust, and government support, which were tested to determine their impact on the adoption of internet banking. A survey was distributed to 103 respondents via mail in Uzbekistan, and the collected data was later analyzed using correlation and linear regression methods. The results confirmed the significance of the selected variables for internet banking adoption. The research also applied several models, including the Technology Acceptance Model, which many prior studies had overlooked.

Key words: e-commerce, IT, internet banking, perceived usefulness, customer adoption, services, perceived ease of use, banks, benefits for Uzbekistan.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot ishi O'zbekiston mijozlari orasida internet-banking xizmatidan foydalanishga ta'sir qiluvchi turli omillarni o'rganishga bag'ishlangan empirik tadqiqotdir. Tadqiqot maqsadida ko'rib chiqilgan o'zgaruvchilar sifatida qabul qilingan naflilik, idrok etilgan foydalanish qulayligi, ishonch va davlat yordami sinovdan o'tkazildi hamda ular internet-bankingni qo'llashga ta'sir etuvchi omillarni aniqlash uchun baholandi. So'rovnomaga O'zbekistondagi 103 respondentga pochta orqali tarqatildi. Keyinchalik to'plangan ma'lumotlar tahlil qilindi, o'zaro bog'liqligi o'rganildi va chiziqli regressiya tahlili amalga oshirildi. Natijalar tanlangan o'zgaruvchilarning internet-banking xizmatidan foydalanishni tushuntirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega ekanini ko'rsatdi. Tadqiqotda, ilgari ko'plab tadqiqotchilar e'tibordan chetda qoldirgan texnologiyani qabul qilishning turli modellari ham qo'llanildi.

Kalit so'zlar: elektron tijorat, IT, internet-banking, qabul qilingan naflilik, mijozlarni moslashuvi, xizmatlar, qabul qilingan foydalanish qulayligi, banklar, O'zbekiston uchun afzalliklar.

Аннотация: Данная исследовательская работа представляет собой эмпирическое исследование различных факторов, влияющих на принятие интернет-банкинга клиентами из Узбекистана. В рамках данного исследования были изучены различные переменные, такие как воспринимаемая полезность, воспринимаемая простота использования, доверие и государственная поддержка, с целью выявления различных факторов, влияющих на принятие интернет-банкинга клиентами из Узбекистана. Опрос был разослан 103 респондентам из Узбекистана по почте. После этого данные были проанализированы и сопоставлены, а для собранной информации был проведен линейный регрессионный анализ. Результаты показали полезность переменных, использованных в работе. В исследовании использовались многие модели, которые многие предыдущие исследователи игнорировали, в частности, модель принятия технологий.

Ключевые слова: электронная коммерция, ИТ, интернет-банкинг, воспринимаемая полезность, взаимодействие с клиентами, услуги, воспринимаемая простота использования, банки, преимущества для Узбекистана.

INTRODUCTION

In modern Internet technology has swiftly developed in many business environments and which are mainly used for improvements in their performances. According to Saffu et al. (2008) there is a remarkable raise in applications of the ecommerce business in the last ten years. There are a lot of benefits of using this ecommerce study and some of them are reduction in cost, improved business chance and decreased lead time providing the consumers with more significant options. (Turban et al., 2008) One of the most important ecommerce instrument is the acceptance of the internet banking model among the clients, the IT tools have positively provided a vast maintain to the services presented by the banking industry (Dawes & Rowley, 1998) There are a lot of banks in the world contribution this great technology and their services using the internet and this technology is developing quickly in the world including Uzbekistan.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

This research is an empirical study about the various variables which influence the adoption of internet banking facility among Uzbekistan customers. The various variables examined for this research purpose were Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, trust, and government support were tested in order to determine their effects on the adoption of internet banking among Uzbekistan customers. Modern Internet technology has swiftly developed in many business environments and is mainly used for improvements in their performances. According to Saffu et al. (2008) there is a remarkable raise in applications of the e-commerce business in the last ten years. There are a lot of benefits of using this e-commerce study and some of them are reduction in cost, improved business chance and decreased lead time providing the consumers with more significant options (Turban et al., 2008). One of the most important e-commerce instrument is the acceptance of the internet banking model among the clients, the IT tools have positively provided a vast maintenance to the services presented by the banking industry (Dawes & Rowley, 1998). Many banks in the world are using this technology in their operations and their services use internet. The internet banking technology is developing quickly round the world including Uzbekistan.

Internet banking can be explained as the bank distribution channel. Researchers give different views on internet banking definition. According to Daniel (1999) and W.Lang (2000), using new electronic and technical development, customers can directly transfer amounts, and can easily use banking services by internet or electronic banking. Electronic or internet banking refers to different types of facilities and services by computer network, and mobile phone, by which bank clients can ask for information and also do retail banking facilities and services (Mols 1998).

In 1991, the banking system in Uzbekistan changed rapidly. The conventional services of banks are declining with the introduction of internet banking. This trend is similar to that happened in the US whereby financial system witnessed the most banks reduced from 55 banks in 1951 to 28 banks in 1993 (Shapiro, Carl and Katz, Michael L. (1994)

In Uzbekistan, fast economic development takes place in Tashkent, the capital city of Uzbekistan. Many banks are located in Tashkent since it is also the centre of commerce and trade for Uzbekistan. Banks in Tashkent have improved customer services by using internet banking adoption. Asaka Bank, Hamkorbank, Kapital Bank, Public Bank, Micro Credit Bank offer their internet banking services to customers. Today, Trust bank, Turon bank, Asaka bank in Tashkent that is the financial markets provide internet banking services for customers.

In this research, the researcher aims to determine internet banking acceptance in Tashkent by customer view. As market is more competitive nowadays, internet banking providers compete to become a greater market. It is extremely significant for market development to create brand customer loyalty. That is very vital for internet banking providers to develop their qualities for the consumers. Although safety cases have improved, they are making a problem for the clients. Facility excellence and also modernisations need main concern in internet banking management (ABA, 2004).

There are many non-financial organizations as well that occasionally challenge banks with new technologies. This research focuses on the influence of such technologies on the banking industry, with particular emphasis on banks in Uzbekistan. The main objective of the study is to determine how banks measure the value and performance of internet banking. The use of the internet has developed significantly, and it is now easy for customers to contact their banks online. However, it is important to understand how this innovation is being adapted and how it can be made safer. Current challenges are largely related to cultural factors or a lack of knowledge, which makes this investigation highly relevant (Goi, 2007).

According to Lamb R. et al. (2005), internet banking allows customers to check balances, view transactions, pay bills, transfer money between accounts, and manage credit card payments — benefits enabled by innovative technology. Internet banking services are available twenty-four hours a day, seven days a week, and transactions are processed instantly, often faster than through ATMs. However, the main question remains: how safe is it, and how well do people adapt to it? (Cooper, 2006).

Most banks provide internet banking to deliver faster and more convenient services to their customers. These qualities of internet banking reflect its growing importance in today's dynamic business environment (Bruno, 2006). Customers with internet access can easily check account balances, make payments, and transfer funds between accounts. Nevertheless, concerns over security remain one of the main reasons why some people hesitate to use internet banking. The purpose of internet banking is to allow customers to access their accounts quickly and conduct financial transactions at any time without obstacles, but the issue of security continues to be a major concern for both banks and customers.

So far, there has been no systematic investigation into how customers in Uzbekistan perceive the security of internet banking, particularly regarding its usefulness and ease of use. Different population groups respond

differently to internet banking. For example, young people are generally quicker to accept modern technologies, while older generations often face difficulties in using internet banking and adapting to new changes (Huaang, 2008). To promote wider adoption of internet banking across all demographics, it is necessary to conduct interviews with both younger and older customers to understand their perceptions and ability to use such services. Currently, there is a lack of data regarding customer feedback on internet banking by age groups and their level of trust in these services.

Another important problem is the role of government support in the development of internet banking, which has not yet been thoroughly investigated. Developing countries like Uzbekistan could achieve significant progress in banking services with stronger government support in information management technologies, ICT companies, and the establishment of an effective legal infrastructure.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology for this study is based on a quantitative approach. Primary data were collected through a structured questionnaire distributed to 103 respondents in Uzbekistan. The collected data were analyzed using correlation and linear regression to examine the relationships between variables such as perceived usefulness, ease of use, trust, and government support, allowing the identification of key factors influencing internet banking adoption.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Details of the additional statistical analysis, research design, questionnaire development and format, and construct measurement was also discussed. This chapter presents the frequencies and statistics generated using SPSS(Version16.0) from the sample responses taken from Uzbekistan. Results of the hypothesis tests relating to each objective, the empirical results, and the findings are also discussed (Table 1).

Table 1. Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Test

Variables	Cronbach'S Alpha
Usefulness	0.678
Ease of use	0.645
Trust	0.922
Government	0.750
Internet Banking	0.954

Table 1 presents the results of the reliability test for both dependent and independent variables, including perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, trust, government support, and internet banking.

Perceived usefulness: The reliability test result indicated a value of 0.678, which shows that the variable "perceived usefulness" meets the assumption of reliability and is suitable for further analysis. This aligns with Nunnally's assumption (1978), which states that any Cronbach Alpha value between 0.70 and 0.90 or higher is considered reliable.

Perceived ease of use: This variable obtained a value of 0.645, suggesting that it is also suitable for further analysis. Hence, perceived ease of use can be regarded as a reliable construct.

Trust: The variable trust demonstrated a very high reliability value of 0.922, which signifies that it is strongly reliable and can be confidently applied for further research.

Government: Government support as a variable showed a reliability value of 0.750, which falls within the acceptable range proposed by previous researchers. Therefore, it can be considered a reliable variable.

Internet Banking: When combining all four dimensions to measure reliability, internet banking achieved a very high value of 0.954. This indicates that it is a highly reliable construct for further research.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The findings of this study have both theoretical and practical significance. From a practical perspective, the results provide valuable insights for banking institutions and internet banking practitioners in formulating strategies to enhance adoption. The study suggests that banks in Uzbekistan could increase internet banking adoption by emphasizing its usefulness and practicality. For instance, banks could organize free training courses on internet banking and make them widely accessible through their branches across the country.

From a theoretical perspective, the findings contribute to the broader literature on IT adoption. The application of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) demonstrates its usefulness in gaining support from various stakeholders, including customers, government institutions, and bank management. Moreover, environmental and cultural factors are shown to play an important role in influencing the adoption of internet banking.

In summary, the adoption of internet banking in Uzbekistan could be significantly increased if people recognize its benefits in terms of perceived usefulness and ease of use. Trust remains a central factor, making the issue of security a priority for both banks and policymakers. Furthermore, government involvement is crucial in supporting the growth of internet banking.

It is important to note that this research tested only a limited number of variables due to time constraints. Future studies should investigate additional factors that may influence the adoption of internet banking.

List of used literature:

1. Daniel, E. (1999). Provision of electronic banking in the UK and the Republic of Ireland. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, Vol 17 No. 2, pp. 72-82.
2. Karen Furst, William W. Lang. and Daniel E. (2000), "Who Offers Internet Banking?" *Quarterly Journal*, Vol. 19, No.2, June.
3. Shapiro, Carl and Katz, Michael L. (1994), "System Competition and Network Effects", *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, Vol.8 (2), Spring 1994, pp. 93-115.
4. Internet banking" in *Journal of Association for Information Systems*, Vol.1 Article 5, July 2000
5. Lamb.R., & Davidson, E. (2005. Winter). Understanding Intranets in the context of end-user computing. *The Data Base for Advances in Information Systems: SIGMIS-ACM Journal Press*, 36(1), 64-85.
6. Horsfield, Richard (2000). "Shaping the future of online financial services," *The Banker*, January. "E-Finance in Asia" Press: *The Internet's Impact on Uzbekistan Banks*, Equity Research Uzbekistan: Industry Report.
7. *Wall Street Journal*, (September 21, 2000), "Teenager trader runs afoul of the SEC as stock touting draws charges of fraud".
8. <http://www.lisa.org/ElectronicBanking.761.0.html>
9. <http://www.uzinvest.uz>

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 8

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelamasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin.
Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>
